

A Program Evaluation of a Patient and Family Advisory Council

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Background

- Patient and Family Advisory Councils (PFAC) enhance patient care and community engagement
- Patient Family Advisors (PFA) are volunteers who provide input to improve the quality of clinical services, population needs, patient access, patient satisfaction, and equity
- Literature supports the value of PFAs in a multitude of healthcare settings
- Quantitative evidence of PFACs' impact, outcomes, and effectiveness to drive meaningful change is lacking

Problem Statement

- The literature lacks validated tools that measure and evaluate the value and impact of PFACs in healthcare systems
- There is no quantitative evidence of a PFACs outcomes and PFA demographic relevance to its hospital population

Purpose Statement

To conduct a program evaluation using 4 measures that were developed, implemented, and evaluated to determine the effectiveness of a PFAC that incorporates the patient, family, and community voice. The 4 tools include the following:

- 1 PFA Satisfaction
- 2 PFAC Staff Member Satisfaction
- 3 LP Satisfaction
- 4 PFAC Outcomes and Demographic Tracking Tool

Theoretical Framework: The Logic Model

Methods

- Setting: 600-bed academic public safety-net hospital for the medically underserved in Los Angeles, CA
- Project Design: Mixed design of qualitative, quantitative, and descriptive analytics

Results

- Despite COVID-19 restrictions, the PFAs had membership on 8 hospital committees, 23 hospital projects, and volunteered 213 hours
- Leadership Partners rated PFAC input and guidance at 5/5 and noted all projects should have PFA input
- English preferred PFAs rated language needs being met by 20% > than Spanish preferred PFAs
- Co-designed COVID vaccine project accomplished 14,963 patient vaccinations

Results

Patient Family Advisor Demographics

Motivation for Joining the Patient Family Advisory Council

Patient Family Advisor by Age

Medical Center Demographics

Med. Center Patient Population by Age

Discussion

Ratings of the evaluation tools showed clear value of the PFAC to the Medical Center

The PFAC population demographic matched the Medical Center patient population, thus provided a meaningful patient perspective

Ensuring co-designed project results are shared with PFAs increased their retention and satisfaction.

Future Implications

Implement PFAC tools at the Medical Center's network hospitals and Patient and Family Centered Care Collaborative PFACs